

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Systematic discovery of cell and immune function in IBD: a lysosomal defect in IBD.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The lysosomal defect affected, was associated with or was derived from the functions of genes from the *BORCS* gene family and the phenotype featured LAMP dysregulation.